

The first DNA-assisted record of *Hemelytrobllatta livida* (Blattodea: Corydiidae) from Georgia with notes on Corydiinae species composition in the Caucasus

Armen Seropian¹, Eka Arsenashvili¹, Natalia Bulbulashvili², Lasha-Giorgi Japaridze³,
Aleqsandre Zukakishvili¹, Shota Japarashvili¹, Aleks Memishishi¹, Levan Mumladze⁴

¹ Institute of Ecology, Ilia State University, Cholokashvili av. 3/5 Tbilisi, 0162, Georgia

² Rustaveli st. 8, 1400, Gori, Georgia

³ David Reqtori st. 55, 2200, Telavi, Georgia

⁴ Institute of Zoology, Ilia State University, Cholokashvili av. 3/5 Tbilisi, 0162, Georgia

<http://zoobank.org/C65A6E9C-CD72-4324-BED5-667E1D2C754C>

Corresponding author: Armen Seropian (armen.seropiani@iliauni.edu.ge)

Academic editor: Asmus Schröter ♦ Received: 8 March 2023 ♦ Accepted: 19 April 2023 ♦ Published: 2 May 2023

Abstract

The fossorial sand cockroach *Hemelytrobllatta livida* (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1865) is reported from Georgia for the first time, with a commentary on the species composition of the Corydiinae Saussure, 1864 subfamily in the Caucasus. Collection data, pictures of the male and female, and DNA barcodes are also provided. Furthermore, information on *Polyphaga aegyptiaca* (Linnaeus, 1758) is provided, along with images of the male, female, and juvenile.

Key words

Dictyoptera, CaBOL, faunistics, sand cockroach, South-Caucasus

Introduction

The subfamily Corydiinae Saussure, 1864 is the most diverse and most studied subfamily in the family Corydiidae Saussure, 1864. These cockroaches known under the collective name “sand cockroaches” are mainly distributed in arid regions and expose a strong sexual dimorphism, with males being macropterous and females generally apterous (such females are fossorial and possess special adaptations for subterranean life). Although females of several genera, including *Ergaula* Walker, 1868 (Grandcolas 1997), *Eucorydia* Hebard, 1929 (Qiu et al. 2017b; Yanagisawa et al. 2021a, 2021b, 2021c), *Homoeogamia* Burmeister 1838; (Estrada-Alvarez and Guadarrama 2013), *Hypercompsa* Saussure, 1864 (Crespo et al. 2015), *Polyphagoidea* Mackerras, 1968 (Mackerras 1968) and *Therea* Billberg, 1820 (Grandcolas 1993) are known to have wings. The reclusive

lifestyle of Corydiinae, along with the unfortunate reputation of these sadly neglected insects has always been an obstacle for the study and collection for a long time, with the most recent and major revisions performed on the most species-rich North American genus *Arenivaga* Rehn, 1903 (Hopkins 2014) and Oriental genera *Eupolyphaga* Chopard, 1929 (Qiu et al. 2018b) and *Eucorydia* (Qiu et al. 2017b; Yanagisawa et al. 2021a, 2021b, 2021c).

The most significant work on the taxonomy of Corydiinae has been performed by Chopard (1929), who recognized 54 species within 10 genera in the Palearctic Region, of which 7 genera and 23 species were new. Bey-Bienko (1950) did the more recent comprehensive work dedicated to Corydiinae and Blattodea overall of the former USSR countries, recognizing 5 genera and 10 species, namely *Anisogamia tamerlana* Saussure, 1893, *Eupolyphaga sinensis* (Walker, 1868), *Hemelytrobllatta incerta* (Chopard, 1929), *H. livida*

(Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1865), *H. minuta* (Bey-Bienko, 1935), *H. roseni* (Brancsik, 1898), *Mononychoblatta semenovi* Chopard, 1929, *Polyphaga aegyptiaca* (Linnaeus, 1758), *P. plancyi* Bolívar, 1883 and *P. saussurei* (Dohrn, 1888). While most of these species are of Central Asian origin, only two species of the subfamily occur in the Caucasus – *H. livida* and the most widely distributed *P. aegyptiaca*, also known from Georgia. Since then, no studies on this group of ancient insects have been performed within the country, and here we report *H. livida* from Georgia for the first time.

Materials and methods

Sample collection and processing

Specimens of *Hemelytrobllatta livida* were collected within the framework of the Caucasus Barcode of Life (CaBOL) project by the CaBOL team of the Institute of Ecology, Ilia State University (<https://ggbc.eu/>). Male specimens were collected at night by hand with flashlights in xerothermic places on vegetation or via pitfall traps filled with vinegar. Female specimens were collected during the day by hand under the rocks, then preserved in 96% ethanol and deposited in the collection of Ilia State University.

Photos of the pre-cleaned from dust and grease adult male and female of *Hemelytrobllatta livida* (Plate 1: A, B, C, D) were taken with a Canon EOS 60D camera and Canon EF-S 60mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens, while an adult male, female, and juvenile of *Polyphaga aegyptiaca* (Plate 1. E, F, G, H) were taken using a Canon EOS 550D camera and Canon EF 100 mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens. Digital images were prepared using Zerene Stacker image stacking software and Adobe Photoshop CS6. For specimen identification, we followed Brunner (1882), Chopard (1929), and Bey-Bienko (1950). Specimens of *P. aegyptiaca* examined during this research are deposited in the collections of Ilia State University.

Institutional abbreviations: ISUIE – Ilia State University, Institute of Ecology; ISUIZ – Ilia State University, Institute of Zoology.

DNA processing

DNA was extracted from tissue samples using the Quick-DNA Magbead Plus Kit (Zymo Research). Partial sequence of cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) was amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the primer pairs LCO1490-JJ and HCO2198-JJ (Astrin and Stüben 2008). Thermal conditions included denaturation at 95°C for 1 min, followed by the first cycle set (15 cycles): 94°C for 30 sec., annealing at 55°C for 1 min (–1°C per cycle), and extension at 72°C for 1:30 min. Second cycle set (25 cycles): 94°C for 35 sec., 45°C for 1 min., 72°C for 1:30 min., and a final extension step at 72°C for 5 min. PCR amplicons were visualized on 1% agarose gels using 1.7 µl of PCR product. Sequencing of the unpurified PCR products in both directions was conducted at the Beijing Genomics Institute (Hong Kong, CN) by using the amplification primers. Sequence analysis was performed using Geneious

Prime 2022.1.1 (<http://www.geneious.com>). Extracted DNA was deposited in the scientific collections of Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia, and aliquots will be deposited at LIB Biobank at Museum Koenig, Bonn, Germany, while the sequences have been submitted to Barcode of Life Data System (BOLD) databases. The newly obtained DNA barcodes of COI sequences were checked out against the BOLD Systems database (<http://www.boldsystems.org/index.php>). The Barcode Index Number (BIN) (Ratnasingham and Hebert 2013) for the sequenced taxa and for their nearest neighbor in BOLD systems (if they had a BIN) are also given. For the calculation of sequence differentiation, we used the k2p distance as performed in the BOLD system

Results

From the collected material, 6 specimens were submitted for the barcoding pipeline, and 4 quality, BOLD compliant barcodes (658 bp length, with no stop codons, indels, or deletions) representing 2 species have been generated so far. Barcode information is given under each barcoded species listed below.

Taxonomic account

Family Corydiidae Saussure, 1864 Genus *Hemelytrobllatta* Chopard, 1929

Hemelytrobllatta livida (Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1865)

Materials examined. GEORGIA • 1♂; Dighomi village (8 km E of Tbilisi); N41.7807°, E44.7021°; 734 m a.s.l.; heathland, xerothermic slope, on *Rhamnus pallasii* at night; leg: A Seropian and L-G Japaridze; 10 Sep 2020; CaBOL-ID 1009797 (Fig. 1A,B). • 1♂; same locality; on *Pyrus salicifolia* at night; leg: A Seropian and L-G Japaridze; 11 Sep 2020. • 1♂; Didgori (10 km E of Tbilisi); N41.7855°, E44.6764°; 801 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, slope with loose soil; leg: A Seropian and L-G Japaridze; 20 Sep 2020. • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7300°, E44.7048°; 710 m a.s.l.; heathland, xerothermic slope, on vegetation at night; leg: L-G Japaridze; 02 Nov 2020. • 1♀; Kumisi; N41.6259°, E44.8111°; 657 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg: S Japarashvili; 25 Sep 2021; CaBOL-ID 1013031. • 1♀; Kvernaki ridge (Gori); N41.9848°, E44.1389°; 696 m a.s.l.; heathland, under rock; leg: N Bulbulashvili; 24 Oct 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020260 (Fig. 1C,D).

Genetics. We obtained a single barcode from the specimen with CaBOL-ID 1020260 (BOLD: AEP4515). Neither the species nor its congeners are present in BOLD as we provide the first COI sequence.

Remarks. The records of *H. livida* in the Caucasus region are known from Julfa and Ordubad (Azerbaijan) (Bey-Bienko 1950), and our records from Georgia extend its known distribution range by almost 680 km to the north-east. Originally described from Cyprus (Brunner von Wattenwyl 1865), the species is also known to occur in Greece (Chopard 1929), Iran, Iraq, Syria, and Turkey (Bey-Bienko 1950; Caesar et al. 2015). Due to the hidden lifestyle of *H. livida*,

Figure 1. A-D: *Hemelytrobatta livida*. A-B: Male, dorsal and ventral view. C-D: Female, dorsal and ventral view. E-H: *Polyphaga aegyptiaca*. E-F: Male and female, dorsal view. G-H: Nymph, dorsal and ventral view. Scale bars = 2 mm.

little is known about its phenology, and there is no information on its reproductive biology, which is likely somewhat similar to that of other congeners. The general appearance of males and females as well as the somatic characteristics correspond well to the descriptions and drawings by Chopard (1929) and Bey-Bienko (1950). Bey-Bienko also mentions the small differences in coloration between specimens from Parnassus (Greece) and Azerbaijan compared to the conspecifics originating from Asia Minor and Central Asia, with the first ones sometimes being more brightly colored with almost no dark spots on elytra. The juveniles strongly resemble the adult females, but with more prominent ornamentation.

Genus *Polyphaga* Brullé, 1835

Polyphaga aegyptiaca (Linnaeus, 1758)

Materials examined. GEORGIA • 1♂; Dighomi village (8 km E of Tbilisi); N41.7805°, E44.7034°; 775 m a.s.l.; heathland, under rocks at night; leg: A Seropian and L-G Japaridze; 13 Sep 2020; CaBOL- ID 1010347 (Fig. 1E). • 1♀; Dighomi village (8 km E of Tbilisi); N41.7805°, E44.7034°; 775 m a.s.l.; heathland, under rocks at night; leg: A Seropian and L-G Japaridze; 05 Sep 2020; CaBOL- ID 1010359 (Fig. 1F). • 1juv.; Dighomi village (8 km E of Tbilisi); N41.7776°,

E44.7132°; 654 m a.s.l.; heathland, under artificial garbage; leg. A Zukakishvili; 03 May 2021; CaBOL- ID 1021022 (Fig. 1G-H). • 2♀♀; 2juv.; Uplistsikhe; N41.966004°, E44.219267°; 563 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. L Mumladze; 02 Sep 2010; ISUIZ. • 1♂♂, 3♀♀; Chachuna Managed Reserve; N41.29366°, E45.95407°; 400 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; 19 Oct 2020; ISUIZ.

Genetics. We obtained two identical barcodes from the specimens with CaBOL-IDs 1010347 and 1010359 (BOLD: AEP4515) and provided the first COI sequences of *P. aegyptiaca*.

Remarks. The distribution range of the species covers the entire Mediterranean region, the southern parts of Europe, and southwestern Asia, reaching Iran in the east. With such a wide distribution, one might think it's a well-studied species in Georgia. In fact, there is almost no location-specific data on *P. aegyptiaca* finds in Georgia, as we provide one based on the material collected within CaBOL, museum material, and also photographic observations available at the Georgian Biodiversity Database (Tarkhnishvili et al. 2013), iNaturalist, and the Facebook group "Wildlife in Georgia". The distribution in Georgia is as follows: Batumi (Bey-Bienko 1950), Chachuna Managed Reserve, Gori, Kumisi, Tbilisi, Rustavi, Poladauri, Kutaisi, Mtskheta, and Uplistsikhe.

Discussion

The taxonomy of Corydiidae has significantly progressed in the last decade, indicating greater species diversity within the family (Gutierrez 2012; Estrada-Álvarez and Guadarrama 2013; Qiu et al. 2016, 2017a, 2017b, 2018a, 2018b; Lucanas 2018; Yanagisawa et al. 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). However, the DNA-based phylogenetic works are not that optimistic due to the difficulty in obtaining specimens (Djernæs et al. 2012, 2015; Legendre et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2017). Further targeted studies of these invertebrates may shed some light on their actual diversity, distribution within the country and phylogenetic relationships.

Acknowledgements

The project on which this study is based was funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research under the grant number 01DK20014A. The responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. We thank the anonymous reviewer and Asmus Schröter for their valuable comments on the manuscript.

References

Astrin JJ, Stüben PE (2008) Phylogeny in cryptic weevils: molecules, morphology and new genera of western Palaearctic Cryptorhynchinae (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Invertebrate systematics* 22(5): 503–522. <https://doi.org/10.1071/IS07057>

Bey-Bienko GY (1950) Nasekomye tarakanovye. Fauna SSSR. Novaya seriya [Cockroach insects. Fauna of the USSR. New series]. Akademii Nauk SSSR, Moscow, 344 pp. [In Russian]

Brunner von Wattenwyl C (1865) *Nouveau Système des Blattaires*. Vienne, Austria, 426 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.5652>

Burmeister H (1838) Erste (26.) Familie. Kakerlaken, Schaben. *Blattaria. Handbuch der Entomologie* 2: 469–517.

Estrada-Álvarez JC, Guadarrama R (2012) Primeros registros de *Homoeogamia mexicana* Burmeister, 1838 (Polyphagidae: Blattaria) para el Estado de México. *Dugesiana* 19(1): 11–12. [In Spanish]

Caesar M, Roy R, Legendre F, Grandcolas P, Pellens R (2015) Catalogue of Dictyoptera from Syria and neighbouring countries (Lebanon, Turkey, Iraq and Jordan). *Zootaxa* 3948(1): 71–92. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3948.1.5>

Chopard L (1929) Orthoptera palaeartica critica VII. Les Polyphagiens de la faune paléarctique (Orth., Blatt.). *Eos* 5: 223–358.

Crespo FA, Di Iorio O, Valverde ADC (2015) Contributions to the knowledge of *Hypercompsa*, new register from Argentina (Blattaria: Corydiidae). *Revista de la Sociedad Entomológica Argentina* 74(3–4): 203–207.

Djernæs M, Klass KD, Picker MD, Damgaard J (2012) Phylogeny of cockroaches (Insecta, Dictyoptera, Blattodea), with placement of aberrant taxa and exploration of out-group sampling. *Systematic Entomology* 37(1): 65–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.2011.00598.x>

Djernæs M, Klass KD, Eggleton P (2015) Identifying possible sister groups of Cryptoceridae + Isoptera: A combined molecular and morphological phylogeny of Dictyoptera. *Molecular phylogenetics and evolution* 84: 284–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2014.08.019>

Estrada-Álvarez JC, Guadarrama C (2013) Una especie nueva de Myrmecoblatta Mann, 1914 (Blattaria: Polyphagidae: Latindiinae) de México. *Boletín de la Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa* 52: 93–95.

Grandcolas P (1993) Le genre *Therea* Billberg, 1820: position phylogénétique, nouvelles espèces, répartition, valence écologique (Dictyoptera, Blattaria, Polyphaginae). *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 71(9): 1816–1822. <https://doi.org/10.1139/z93-259> [In French]

Grandcolas P (1997) Habitat use and population structure of a polyphagine cockroach, *Ergaula capensis* (Saussure 1893) (Blattaria Polyphaginae) in Gabonese rainforest. *Tropical Zoology* 10(2): 215–222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03946975.1997.10539338>

Gutiérrez E (2012) Especie nueva del género de cucarachas Compsodes (Dictyoptera: Blattaria: Corydiidae) para la República Dominicana. *Solenodon* 10: 52–62.

Hopkins H (2014) A revision of the genus *Arenivaga* (Rehn) (Blattodea, Corydiidae), with descriptions of new species and key to the males of the genus. *ZooKeys* (384): 1–256. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.384.6197>

Legendre F, Nel A, Svenson GJ, Robillard T, Pellens R, Grandcolas P (2015) Phylogeny of Dictyoptera: Dating the Origin of Cockroaches, Praying Mantises and Termites with Molecular Data and Controlled Fossil Evidence. *PLoS ONE* 10(7): e0130127. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0130127>

Lucañas CC (2018) A New Latindiine Cockroach, *Gapudipentax guttingi* gen. et sp. n. (Blattodea: Corydiidae: Latindiinae) from the Philippines. *Halteres* 9: 151–156. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1418609>

Mackerras MJ (1968) Polyphagidae (Blattodea) from eastern Australia. *Australian Journal of Entomology* 7(2): 147–154. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-6055.1968.tb00722.x>

Qiu L, Che YL, Wang Z (2016) *Sinolatindia petila* gen. n. and sp. n. from China (Blattodea, Corydiidae, Latindiinae). *ZooKeys* 596: 27–38. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.596.8332>

Qiu L, Che YL, Wang ZQ (2017a) Contribution to the cockroach genus *Tenoneura* Hanitsch, 1925 (Blattodea: Corydiidae: Corydiidae) with descriptions of seven new species from China. *Zootaxa* 4237(2): 265–299. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4237.2.3>

- Qiu L, Che YL, Wang ZQ (2017b) Revision of *Encorydia* Hebard, 1929 from China, with notes on the genus and species worldwide (Blattodea, Corydioidea, Corydiidae). *ZooKeys* 709: 17–56. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.709.14755>
- Qiu L, Che YL, Wang ZQ (2018a) Contributions to some Corydiinae genera (Blattodea: Corydioidea: Corydiidae) from China. *Journal of Natural History* 52 (21-22): 1433–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2018.1463406>
- Qiu L, Che YL, Wang ZQ (2018b) A taxonomic study of *Eupolyphaga* Chopard, 1929 (Blattodea: Corydiidae: Corydiinae). *Zootaxa* 4506(1): 1–68. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4506.1.1>
- Ratnasingham S, Hebert PD (2013) A DNA-based registry for all animal species: the Barcode Index Number (BIN) system. *PloS one* 8(7): e66213. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066213>
- Tarkhnishvili D, Chaladze G, Gavashelishvili A, Javakhishvili Z, Mumladze L (2013) Georgian biodiversity database. <http://www.biodiversity-georgia.net> [Accessed 20 February 2023]
- Wang Z, Shi Y, Qiu Z, Che Y, Lo N (2017) Reconstructing the phylogeny of Blattodea: robust support for interfamilial relationships and major clades. *Scientific Reports* 7(3907): 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-04243-1>
- Yanagisawa S, Hiruta SF, Sakamaki Y, Liao JR, Shimano S (2021a) Two new species of the genus *Encorydia* (Blattodea: Corydiidae) from the Nansei Islands in southwest Japan. *Zoological science* 38(1): 90–102. <https://doi.org/10.2108/zs200048>
- Yanagisawa S, Hiruta SF, Sakamaki Y, Shimano S (2021b) A new species of the genus *Encorydia* (Blattodea: Corydiidae) from the Miyako-jima Island in Southwest Japan. *Species Diversity* 26(2): 145–151. <https://doi.org/10.12782/specdiv.26.145>
- Yanagisawa S, Sakamaki Y, Jantarit S, Shimano S (2021c) A New Species of the Genus *Encorydia* (Blattodea: Corydiidae) from Chiang Mai in Northern Thailand. *Species Diversity* 26(2): 191–195. <https://doi.org/10.12782/specdiv.26.191>